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University-Industry Collaboration And Education Delivery In Imo State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined university-industry collaboration and education delivery in Imo State, Nigeria. Two (2) objectives, two (2) research questions and two (2) corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The study was guided by theory of x-efficiency. The study adopted correlational survey design. The population of the study comprised all the 1,628 academic staff and 2,468 administrative staff in Imo State University, Federal University of Technology and Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education. A sample size of 230 staff was drawn from a total population of 4,096 staff using Taro Yamane minimum sample size. The study used two sets of instrument for data collection. The first instrument is titled: “University Industry Collaboration Questionnaire (UICQ)” while the second is titled: “Education Delivery Questionnaire (EDQ)”. Simple regression was used to answer research questions while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument for this study was validated for face and content validity using the supervisors and three experts in the Department of Educational Measurement and Evaluation, University of Port Harcourt. The reliability of the instruments were determined using Cronbach Alpha Statistics. The reliability index of university industry collaboration were given at 0.78 while education delivery were given at 0.86. The findings of the study revealed that university-industry collaboration in students’ industrial training and research relate to educational delivery in Imo State. Based on the findings, the study concluded that university-industry collaboration in students’ industrial training and research among others are strong components of university-industry collaboration and therefore relate to educational delivery in Imo State. Based on the findings and conclusion, the study recommended amongst others that there should be synergy between university administrators, government and private sectors on the provision and maintenance of school infrastructural facilities to enhance education delivery in Imo State.

Keywords: University-Industry, Collaboration, Education Delivery, Imo State, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Internationally, education has been seen as a potent tool for ensuring the progress of development both on the individual basis and the society at large. As a development agent, it is valued by all the nations of the world because it has brought total liberation to man. Education is a source of man’s transformation from ignorance and misery of knowledge and happiness. It enriches peoples’ understanding of themselves and the world and improves the quality of lives and leads to broad social benefits to individuals and society. It has made man useful to himself, his generation and beyond. Education is identified as an effective tool that is capable of breaking the cycle of poverty and lays a strong foundation for socio-economic development of a nation. It develops the human capital of a nation for economic efficiency and social

consistency. The development of the relevant human capital, especially the high level cadre is basically the statutory responsibility of higher education. Uche (2020) opined that the concept of higher education is marked by diversity, that is, there are several terms and phrases used to describe it. Higher education includes higher learning, which often referred to graduate education, down to post-secondary education, which generally referred to the several years following college or secondary school, whether spent in college, university or polytechnic and among others.

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO (2016) defined higher education as educational establishment to which access is available for people who have completed secondary education and in which, the course of study last for not less than three years, but more generally from four years to six years. The observations of the researcher as educational stakeholder showed that higher education has two meanings.

Firstly, it means the next academic level (for just associate and bachelor's degree), (without research) after secondary education as in the case of colleges of education, that offer a post-secondary school education, without any emphasis on the research component, and secondly, it signifies the system of institutions that provides post-secondary school courses and at the same time engages in research (as at the levels of masters and doctorate degrees). For example, the university system, that offers higher education and trains people on how to do research. Nigeria sees higher education as comprising post-secondary education, given in universities colleges of education, polytechnics and monotronics, including institutions offering correspondence courses. University-industry collaboration is the interaction between universities and industries, which mainly aims to encourage knowledge and technical exchange based on mutual benefits and interest. The purpose of this collaboration is for knowledge creation and utilization through the activities of research and development, funding and resources development. The need to carry out an empirical study on university-industry collaboration in higher education delivery in Imo State cannot be overemphasized. This is because universities and industrial collaboration is one of the novel concepts in higher education administration, which is a veritable tool to solve the myriad of problems and difficult challenges facing Nigerian Universities generally and Imo State in particular. It is a partnership that will guarantee mutual benefits to universities and industry. It has also been observed by higher education scholars that universities have a unique role to play in delivery solutions to the sustainable development goals and one of the most efficient ways to do it is to create partnerships to further research and development. Basically, it is the universities that produce the workforce needed by the industries hence the onerous task of collaboration to ensure quality products and areas of need.

The importance of higher education and industry collaboration cannot be underestimated. This importance stems from the fact that it will lead to adequate funding of higher education, allow higher education to acquire international status and global standards, encourage effective and efficient management of higher education, produce the right caliber of manpower needed by the industry, help higher education formed research, allow students industrial training, increase infrastructure and improve entrepreneurial capacity of higher education through students industrial training. Higher education and industry have to work harmoniously for the benefit of each entity. Thus, collaboration means mutual benefit. Collaboration will lead to cost savings, the industry will introduce into the higher education system more efficient and cost effective operations and service delivery. Collaboration will also help in sharing risk between industry and the higher institutions, other benefits include improved level of services, more innovative approaches can be introduced in order to increase the level as well as quality of services, it will also lead to the enhancement of revenue generation.

Campbell and Dunleavy (2016) identified the following components of collaboration such as; students' industrial training and research. The relationship between university-industry collaboration in student's industrial training and higher education in Imo State cannot be overemphasized. There is a growing demand by companies, industries, and other organisations for well-trained graduates with relevant entrepreneurial skills who can be employed to meet the nation's need students' industrial training is the practical training programme that students receive from relevant organizations while still in school, such as Students Industrial Work Experience (SIWES). The scheme is an educational programme designed for students to participate in work activities while still in school. Based on this, students are given the

opportunity to be part of the actual work situation in a work (Emeahera and Chris-Israel, 2017). SIWES is a planned monitored, training and intervention programme centred on specified and specific learning and career goals which leads to the development of participants' occupational skills.

The importance of research in university-industry collaboration in higher education delivery in Imo State cannot be under-estimated. Research implies careful examination of an object or situation for the purpose of effecting development and improvement. It is a way of acquiring dependable and useful information and data about a particular object as well as the analysis of the data collected in order to arrive at a valid conclusion. Accordingly, the primary purpose of research is to discover answers to important questions to resolve socio-economic and political problems. Oyesole (2010) saw research as the application of the scientific method to attain or prove new and exciting theories, search for new ideas, inventions, discoveries and establishment of new knowledge, principles and methods. Collaboration between academics and industry can lead to a range of benefits including the provision of solutions to country's problems, the improvement of standard of living, the improvement of educational practices, the eradication of poverty and ignorance, and national development (Nwankpa, 2023). In addition to improving research and development (R&D), collaborative research between universities and industries has other important benefits.

This study was anchored on Harvey Leibenstein x-efficiency theory that was developed in (1966). The theory of x-efficiency developed by Harvey Leibstein influenced the development of the concept of university industry collaboration in management of public enterprise. Leibenstein's idea as that the expansionary monetary and financial expansionary policies are necessary for ensuring that public enterprises continues to exist efficiently. This notwithstanding inefficiency still exists in public enterprises because of the existence of distortionary government interventions as well as the bureaucratic impediments of the state socio-economic and political structure; sequel to the incidents of inefficiency in public enterprises, Leihenstein, pointed out that public-private participation is a necessary strategy for achieving efficiency in the management of public enterprises.

The theory of x-efficiency basically explains that there are several constraints which impede governments' capacity to ensure effective management of public enterprises and service delivery. Many other factors such as the ones identified by Leibenstein impose defects in government capacity to plan, finance, manage, change and innovation, as well as cater for the various requirements for effective management capacity, led to the rationale for relying on an alternative arrangement for management of public enterprises.

The theory of x-efficiency therefore sees university-industry collaboration as an alternative management practice that will help to ensure that there is adequate supply of public fund, infrastructural facilities as well as effective management of any public concern. This involvement of the private sector will eventually lead to improved management of our higher institutions for the overall good of the masses. Higher institutions are large and complex, thus they require huge investment; thus UIC is relied on to provide the necessary huge investments for the growth and development of higher institutions. This theory finally calls for a dual system-private and public sectors, the strength of the dual system should be harnessed in an integrated fashion to achieve the educational sectors goals and objectives; university industry collaboration represents an alternative economic arrangement to traditional public infrastructural financing and has been widely acknowledge as a potentially important instrument to drive development goals and that is what the ex-efficiency theory advocates.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The management of higher education in Imo State seems to have great challenges. This is because government alone cannot manage education in Nigeria. There is need to involve private sector to also participate in the management of higher education in Imo State for quality delivery.

This is also a way of fulfilling the provisions of the National Policy on Education which identified education as a huge investment and have acknowledged the participation of all stakeholders to its financing and management. However, the situation of university-industry collaboration/partnership appears to be low and therefore affects the management of higher education delivery in the areas of

students' industrial training, research, curriculum development, funding, facilities provision and human resources transformation and development.

Observations of the researcher as an educational stakeholder has shown that if the public and private sectors are involved in the management of higher education, schools will function properly in the area of provision of infrastructural facilities, financial assistance and provision of staff especially lecturers. There is therefore a felt need by the researcher to find out if university-industry collaboration in the areas of students' industrial training and research would enhance higher education delivery in Imo State. Hence, the need to embark on this study.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study generally was to examine university-industry collaboration and education delivery in Imo State. Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. examine the relationship between university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and education delivery in Imo State.
2. determine the relationship between university-industry collaboration in research output and education delivery in Imo State.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions.

1. What is the relationship between university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and education delivery in Imo State?
2. What is the relationship between university-industry collaboration in research and education delivery in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 levels of significance.

- H0₁:** There is no significant relationship between university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and education delivery in Imo State.
- H0₂:** There is no significant relationship between university-industry collaboration in research and education delivery in Imo State.

METHODOLOGY

The research design of the study was correlation survey design. The correlation design was considered appropriate because it enabled the researcher to collect data on variables of university-industry collaboration and education delivery with a view to testing the relationship between them. The population of the study comprised all the 1,628 academic staff and 2,468 administrative staff in Imo State University, Federal University of Technology and Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education. The respondents for the study consisted of academic staff and administrative staff of three selected public universities in Imo State, Owerri, with a total number of 4,096. Source: Imo State University Staff and Students' Nominal Roll, 2023. A sample size of 230 staff was drawn from a total population of 4,096 staff from the three selected public universities in Imo State using Taro Yamane Minimum sampling technique. Simple random sampling technique was used to draw elements into the sample frame. The study used two sets of instrument for data collection. The first instrument were titled: "University-Industry Collaboration Questionnaire (UICQ) while the second were titled: Education Delivery Questionnaire (EDQ)". The structured questionnaire were divided into two (2) sections. Section A elicited responses on personal data, while Section B consisted of 30 items structured in Line with the 6 research questions of this study. The instrument were modified after 4 points Likert scale type of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1 point scale of responses. The instruments for this study were validated for face and content validity using the supervisors and three (3) experts in the Department of Educational Measurement and Evaluation from Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt. This enabled the researcher to obtain a critical assessment of the instrument in terms of appropriateness and adequacy. The suggestions from these experts were used to improve the content of the instrument before administration. The reliability of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha to measure the stability. The instruments yielded reliability indices of 0.78 and 0.86 for

University-Industry Collaboration Questionnaire (UICQ) and Education Delivery Questionnaire (EDQ) respectively. The researcher with the help of three (3) trained research assistants visited the sampled universities in Imo State to administer the questionnaire. A total of 230 copies of the questionnaire were administered out of which 210 were successfully retrieved and used for data analysis. Simple regression was used to answer research questions and t-test associated with simple regression were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and education delivery in Imo State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression on the Relationship between University-Industry Collaboration in Students' Industrial Training and Education Delivery in Imo State

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.796 ^a	.634	.634	.29515

a. Predictors: (Constant), Students' Industrial Training

Table 1 show the results of a linear regression carried out to investigate the relationship between university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and education delivery in Imo State. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.79$), which showed that there was a strong positive relationship between university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and education delivery in Imo State. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) associated with the linear regression (R) of 0.79 was 0.634. This coefficient of determination (R-squared) indicates that, students' industrial training accounted for 63.4% of education delivery in Imo State. This is an indication that other factors affect students' industrial training and education delivery in Imo State accounted for 36.6%. Therefore, there is a strong positive relationship between university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and education delivery in Imo State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between university-industry collaboration in research and education delivery in Imo State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression on the Relationship between University-Industry Collaboration in Research and Education Delivery in Imo State

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.654 ^a	.428	.428	.36898

a. Predictors: (Constant), Research

Table 2 show the results of a linear regression carried out to investigate the relationship between research and education delivery in Imo State. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.65$), which showed that there is a moderate positive relationship between research and education delivery in Imo State. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) associated with the linear regression (R) of 0.79 was 0.428. This coefficient of determination (R-squared) indicates that, research accounted for 42.8% of education delivery in Imo State. This is an indication that other factors affect research and education delivery in Imo State accounted for 57.8%. Therefore, there is a moderate positive relationship between research and education delivery in Imo State.

Result of Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between university-industry collaboration in students’ industrial training and education delivery in Imo State.

Table 3: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Relationship between University-Industry Collaboration in Students’ Industrial Training and Education Delivery in Imo State

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	.297	.025		12.038	.000
	Students’ Industrial Training	.927	.009	.796	107.731	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Higher Education Delivery

Table 3 show the results of simple regression carried out to investigate whether the relationship between university-industry collaboration in students’ industrial training and education delivery in Imo State. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.92$), but students’ industrial training contributed significantly to the model with $\beta = 0.79$ and the significant value of 0.00 was less than $p = 0.05$, which show that there is a

significant relationship between university-industry collaboration in students’ industrial training and education delivery in Imo State. The t-test value 12.038 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected and we accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between university-industry collaboration in students’ industrial training and education delivery in Imo State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between university-industry collaboration in research and education delivery in Imo State.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Relationship between University-Industry Collaboration in Research and Education Delivery in Imo State

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	.824	.030		27.405	.000
	Research	.764	.011	.654	70.805	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Higher Education Delivery

Table 4 show the results of simple regression carried out to investigate whether the relationship between university-industry collaboration in research and education delivery in Imo State. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.76$), but research contributed significantly to the model with $\beta = 0.76$ and the

significant value of 0.000 was less than $p = 0.05$, which show that there is a significant relationship between university-industry collaboration in research and education delivery in Imo State. The t-test value 27.405 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha

level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected and we accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between university-industry collaboration in research and education delivery in Imo State, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between University-Industry Collaboration in Students' Industrial Training and Educational Delivery

The findings from result of analysis of research question one revealed that there is a strong positive relationship between university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and educational delivery in Imo state, Nigeria. This means that to a strong positive relationship, practical experience relates to higher education delivery, problem-solving skills relate to education delivery, professional development relates to education delivery, networking relates to education delivery and guidance and mentorship relates to education delivery. This finding is supported by Isaac (2019) who stated that industrial training or internship is a practical experience in the form of opportunities offered by a company or industry so that students can learn the practical impact of their studies and know about a particular industry. This industrial training is an important method that combines theoretical education and the world of work in accordance with what is needed by society in the business world. In this case industrial training not only provides benefits for students, but also provides mutual benefits between students and industry. Where the industry has the opportunity to obtain competent human resources who have high motivation.

Relationship between University-Industry Collaboration in Research and Education Delivery

The findings from result of analysis of research question two revealed their there is a moderate positive relationship between university-industry collaboration in research and education delivery in Imo state, Nigeria. This means that to a moderate positive relationship, technology transfer relates to education delivery, knowledge transfer relates to education delivery, ICT relates to higher education delivery, collaboration relates to higher education delivery and consultation relates to education delivery. This findings agreed with Karah (2014) who asserted that research is a way to gain better knowledge of technology resources, expert human resources and workforce for government and corporation is crucial for development of corporation bodies including education. This is one of the reasons corporations should contribute to research support at the level of education. This implies that the outcome of research helps corporations in making informed decisions for profit making and attainment of corporate goals. Research links the experience and evidence base that support itself to statistical and drift analyses, collaboration, discovery and ultimately to positive impacts on findings care and safety. Moreover, the explosion of information technology has enabled researchers to easily transcend geographical distances so that they may collaborate to answer important questions in the field.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that university-industry collaboration in students' industrial training and research relate to educational delivery in Imo State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were offered by the researcher.

1. The private sector should be proactive to forge meaningful partnership with the government to ensure adequate financial resource management which is a formidable factor for education delivery.
2. There should be synergy between university administrators, government and private sectors on the provision and maintenance of school infrastructural facilities to enhance education delivery.

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